

VISS

D8.2 – Preliminary Data Management

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Technical references

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* PU = Public- Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page).

SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Document History

v	Date	Beneficiary	Modifications
v0.1	16/02/2024	KVC	First draft of document
v0.2	20/02/2024	ICONS	Revised version based on the comments of Marcelo Bardellini- ICONS
v0.3	28/02/2024	CETEC	Revised version with feedback of Jose Plaza-CETEC
v1.0	29/02/2024	CETEC	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v2.0	04/09/2025	KVC	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, resubmitted to EC, including the mention to the risk of photos taken during public events and the inclusion of this in the participant informed consent form (page 18 in Section 6.1.7 and Annex A, page 21).

Verification and approval v1.0

	Name	Date
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Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	José Antonio Plaza Hernández	29/02/2024

Verification and approval v2.0

	Name	Date
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1. List of abbreviations

D	Deliverable
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DIS	Data Integration System
DAC	Data Access Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, interoperable, and Re-usable
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection
JCA	Joint Controllership Agreement
M	Month
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PC	Project Coordinator
WP	Work Package

2. Executive summary

This is the preliminary version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ViSS project, prepared for the 6-month point in the project. The DMP describes the data management lifecycle, indicating how research data collected, processed, or generated by the ViSS project will be handled during and after the completion of the study. Thus, this deliverable aims to inform the partners about the main guidelines and good practices that will be applied to the data processed and generated in the project. This DMP defines the methodologies and standards that will be applied in ViSS to make the data FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

The DMP has been drafted following the guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon 2020 and the general template annexed to the document¹. The DMP is intended to be a living document in which information will be available at a more detailed and specific level through regular updating as the project implementation progresses and when significant changes or milestones occur. The final version of the DMP will be delivered at month 46.

By adhering to the principles outlined in this Data Management Plan and maintaining compliance with GDPR requirements, the project aims to ensure the protection of personal data throughout its lifecycle.

¹ h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf (europa.eu)

2.1. ViSS Project Summary

The European plastics policy highlights bio-based plastics as a key piece to solve the negative impact of fossil-based plastics in the environment. One of the most promising biodegradable biopolymers is the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) family that can replace these fossil-based plastics in many applications. They are synthesised by microorganisms from renewable carbon sources and exhibit good properties and excellent biodegradability.

In this sense, ViSS project will create a new value chain around PHBV (a copolymer of the PHAs family) as a safe, sustainable, and cost-effective alternative to conventional plastics, especially for short shelf-life food packaging applications due to its excellent properties including flexibility, processability, recyclability and biodegradability in relevant environments (soil, freshwater, marine, industrial composting, and home composting). ViSS PHBV will be produced from industrial organic residues and will be formulated and compounded to be transformed and validated as high-performance food packaging, being mechanically recyclable and biodegradable.

Moreover, the whole ViSS circular value chain will be constructed upon a collaborative approach and under safe and sustainable criteria, accomplishing EU regulations and ensuring policy alignment, while the project will deliver and disseminate digital tools and resources which will favour an increased social readiness and marketability of bio-based plastics, fostering a ViSS wide adoption and replication.

Our project gathers 15 partners from 6 European countries leaders in different fields of knowledge, from bioplastic production to validation in real packaging applications.

Adoption of ViSS value chain will produce relevant outcomes as improved functionalities and environmental performances: reduction of 57.8% of CO₂ emissions compared to fossil counterparts, yearly saving 11.7 kt of crude oil, recirculating 288.95 kt of biomass, avoiding the use of 2.2 kt of hazardous substances.

3. Introduction to the deliverable

3.1. Deliverable objectives and scope

In the context of our scientific research project, the data to be processed primarily comprises research results rather than personal data. The nature of our investigation involves the collection and analysis of scientific information, experimental outcomes, and related datasets. While the predominant focus is on non-personal data, we acknowledge the potential existence of personal data within the research scope. As such, our commitment to data security remains paramount, and we aim to uphold stringent measures to safeguard any incidental personal data that might be processed during the project's lifespan. Our approach aligns with ethical standards, emphasizing the importance of privacy and confidentiality. We assure that any handling of personal data will adhere

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to applicable legal and ethical guidelines, and our data management practices will prioritize the protection of individuals' privacy.

This document aims to define the data the project will generate, how data will be processed, the related compliance with the GDPR, the adoption of methodologies and standards, the strategies for ORDP adherence, and how it will be managed to respect the FAIR principles.

3.2. Data generation and collection

In the context of ViSS technical research project, it is crucial to emphasize that the collection and processing of personal data are not inherent to the project's primary objectives. The project predominantly involves technical aspects, and personal data are not deemed essential for most of its duration.

During the phase of D7.2 Public Engagement, personal data will be processed. As defined in D7.2, this strategy foresees public participation, which can be realised - among others - through information days and surveys.

The basic requirements of data protection are to be always complied with. The consortium commits to implementing appropriate measures to ensure the security and confidentiality of any personal data that may be encountered in the later phases of the project, aligning with ethical considerations and legal requirements.

The participation of stakeholders and citizens will be analysed and determined if necessary to sign an informed consent form. The informed consent will be necessary for non-professional participants in the activities of D7.2, such as surveys during public events.

3.3. Data summary

In the pursuit of our technical research project, the data and results anticipated are unequivocally of a technical nature. The essence of our investigation revolves around acquiring, analysing, and interpreting information derived from experimental processes, scientific observations, and other technical methodologies. Throughout the project's lifespan, our commitment lies in treating the obtained data with methodical rigor and adhering to established standards and protocols. Rigorous procedures will be employed in the systematic collection of data, ensuring that it is meticulously organized and documented in formats conducive to comprehensive analysis. This meticulous approach not only facilitates the extraction of meaningful insights but also contributes to the reproducibility and transparency of our research findings. The utilization of standardized formats and procedures not only enhances the reliability of the collected data but also ensures that it is amenable to scrutiny, replication, and further exploration within the broader scientific community. Our emphasis on methodical data treatment underscores the robustness and integrity of the scientific outcomes anticipated from this project, positioning them as valuable contributions to the broader body of technical knowledge.

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In addition, the Project must define long-term sustainability conditions. To this end, the repository management model must be guided by the following principles:

- Sustainability of ViSS Repository as such.
- Promoting sustainability by design.
- Promoting sustainability by synergies with other Repositories.
- Defining methodologies and protocols to ensure the re-use of the data stored in the repository.

The ViSS Data Repository will process personal data in a GDPR compliant manner. The data obtained from public participants will be anonymized in accordance with GDPR and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) and Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) Guidelines.

The main types of data to be generated can be approximately divided into three different groups:

- Project rules and follow-up data: Grant and Consortium Agreements, Gantt Chart and Actions Plan, administrative and financial data, templates, surveys, and management files.
- Research data: it covers the data collected within the frames of the project subject including analysed data. In a research context, examples of such data include graphs and images, statistical data, parameters, experimental conditions, experimental observations, results of measurements etc. The focus will be on the availability of this research data in digital form.
- Data related to dissemination activities: publications, presentations/posters, seminars/newsletters, dedicated short videos.

3.4 Data size and format

ViSS datasets are various, and the format of the data collected may vary. The Consortium will give preference to open formats (e.g. csv, txt etc.), formats compatible with the use of open-source software, or at least formats that are widely accessible without significant expenses. Most of the datasets will, preferably, be produced and stored in the following formats.

- Text documents: .doc, *.rtf, *.odt or *.pdf
- Spreadsheets: .xls
- Comma separated values: .csv
- Presentation: .ppt or *.pdf
- Image of photo formats: .jpg, *.png
- Audio formats: .mp3
- Video files: .mp4

The data collected during this project is expected to vary significantly in terms of both size and quantity. Due to the dynamic nature of the project and the diversity of data sources, it is challenging to precisely estimate the volume and scope of the data at this stage. Subsequent revisions and iterations will allow for a more detailed specification of the data collected. We anticipate that as the project progresses and more information becomes available, we will be able to provide a clearer understanding of the data requirements. Thank you for your understanding and flexibility as we navigate through this process.

4. Fair Data

To ensure that research data can be used, shared, and re-used it is crucial to take care that those data are accessible, understandable, and usable. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information, and documentation explaining how data were created or digitized, what data mean or what their content and structure are.

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In order to make data findable, the Consortium will adopt the following naming conventions that provides a clear version number by following time sequence (the most recent the most updated version) to make data accessible, understandable, and usable:

DATA_DELIVERABLE NUMER_FILE NAME_PROJECT NAME.FORMAT

The Consortium also will encourage establishing links between data collected and stored and the associated documentation, following recommendations such as the following:

- Including information within the data or document itself, e.g. in the document properties function of a file or the file header.
- Keeping a database of metadata with links to files.
- Storing a readme.txt file alongside the data which provides basic explanatory details. Txt. Files will be acceptable to explain very simple stuff like how to connect to a database, not the database explanation itself.
- Recording relevant context in lab notebooks or associated papers and reports.
- Including link to websites or web pages which explain the context of the research.

4.2. Metadata

The use of common data and metadata standards are a key aspect for semantic and technological data operability. Metadata can describe the content, context, and provenance of datasets in a standardized and structured manner, typically describing the purpose, origin, temporal characteristics, geographic location, authorship, access conditions and terms of use of a dataset. This provides structured searchable information that helps users to find existing data resources, judge whether a particular dataset is suitable for their research purpose and provides a bibliographic record for citing data. Standard dictionaries of metadata will be used for all data types produced by the data creators.

Metadata will include different types of metadata:

- **Descriptive metadata:** describe a resource for retrieval and identification. They may contain elements such as title, abstract, author, keywords, etc.
- **Structural metadata:** relationships between different sets of associated data in the context of databases, such as schema describing associations between tables.
- **Administrative metadata:** provides the information necessary to help process a resource. An example might be the date of creation or how a resource was created. It may contain several subgroups of administrative information. Among the most common are metadata on rights and metadata for long-term preservation. The latter is one of the primary purposes of repositories.

4.2.1. Metadata Templates.

4.2.1.1. Descriptive metadata

Title	[Title of the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Date Created/Published	[Date when the resource was created or published]
Description	[Brief description of the resource, including its content, purpose, or significance]
Subject(s)	[Keywords or phrases that describe the topic(s) or subject(s) of the resource]
Language	[Language(s) of the resource]
Format	[Format of the resource, such as text, image, audio, video, etc.]
Extent	[Physical or digital size of the resource, duration for audio/video, number of pages for text, etc.]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Rights	[Information about the copyright status or usage rights of the resource]
Identifier	[Unique identifier or URL assigned to the resource]
Source	[Information about the origin or source of the resource]
Relation	[Relationship of the resource to other resources, if applicable]
Coverage	[Geographical, temporal, or thematic coverage of the resource]
Audience	[Intended audience or target demographic for the resource]

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Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

4.2.1.2. Structural Metadata Template:

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Hierarchy	[Description of the hierarchical structure of the resource, such as chapters, sections, pages, etc.]
Sequence	[Order or sequence of the components within the resource]
Navigation	[Information about how to navigate or access different parts of the resource]
Relationships	[Information about the relationships between different components or parts of the resource]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Duration	[For multimedia resources, the duration or length of the resource]
Resolution	[For images or videos, the resolution or dimensions]
Bit Rate	[For audio or video files, the bit rate or quality]
Compression	[If applicable, information about compression methods used]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]
Annotations	[Information about any annotations, bookmarks, or metadata embedded within the resource]
Access Restrictions	[Any access restrictions or permissions associated with specific components or parts of the resource]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Keywords	[Additional keywords or phrases relevant to the resource]

4.2.1.3. Administrative metadata:

Resource Identifier	[Unique identifier for the resource]
Creator(s)	[Name(s) of the creator(s) or author(s)]
Contributor(s)	[Names of individuals or organizations that contributed to the creation or development of the resource]
Creation Date	[Date when the resource was created]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
Publication Date	[Date when the resource was published or made available]
Modification Date	[Date when the resource was last modified or updated]
Version	[Version number or information about any revisions or updates]
Publisher	[Entity or individual responsible for making the resource available]
File Format	[Format of the resource, including file extensions and MIME types]
Size	[Size of the resource in bytes or other appropriate units]
Storage Location	[Location where the resource is stored or archived]
Access Rights	[Information about access rights or permissions associated with the resource]
Preservation Metadata	[Information about preservation strategies or metadata necessary for long-term preservation]
Rights Management	[Information about rights management or access control mechanisms]
Metadata Creation	[Details about the process of creating or capturing metadata for the resource]
Metadata Standards	[Information about the metadata standards or schemas used to describe the resource]
Checksums	[Checksum values to verify data integrity]

4.3. Making data accessible

Accessibility means that metadata and data are understandable to humans and machines and may be retrievable by their identifier via a standardised communication protocol.

As foreseen in Article 16 of the Grand Agreement, the partners must grant access to each other's information, subject to the restrictions on intellectual property and any special procedures set out in Annex 5 of the GA.

Data accessibility will be further defined in the final version of this deliverable in terms of:

- Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited taking into consideration that where possible preference should be given to certified repositories supporting open access.
- How will access be provided and if there would be restrictions on use.
- The authentication procedure to authorise data access.

Dissemination of results:

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Open science: open access to scientific publications:

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- At the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- Immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND), and
- Information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

4.4. Making data interoperable

Interoperability is the ability to access and process machine-readable data from multiple sources, sometimes automatically, without that data losing meaning or integrity". To achieve this goal, data requires:

- Syntactic interoperability: widespread adoption of standard data formats, and the implementation of application programming interfaces and connectors that allow data from multiple sources to be accessed and integrated.
- Semantic interoperability: data and information must be exchanged across systems without its context and meaning being lost; and
- Search interoperability: it enables a user to conduct queries across two or more collections of data.

Thus, interoperability enables improved data usability and use. For this reason, putting in practice interoperability will be a priority for the Consortium to have the following benefits (among others):

- Reducing time, effort and expense spent on data collection.
- Eliminating frustration and risks associated with finding inconsistent and incomplete data.
- Making available sustainable, disaggregated data for effective decision-making.

4.5. Increase data re-use

The obtained data by developing the project could be made openly accessible if the Grand Assembly (GA) agrees to. The main aim is to make the data openly accessible for as long as possible. The decision on the long-term availability of the data collected and processed in the framework of the VISS project will be taken as the data are stored.

After the completion of each task involving data collection, the data will be made openly accessible when the following requirements are met:

- Data collection and processing are completed.
- Data checking - in terms of quality control - is performed.
- The exploitation plan of the consortium partners, both in terms of scientific publications and commercial purposes, is finalised.

Discussions on licensing and re-use conditions will also be conducted by the project's GA, with the support and/or supervision of the DPO and the Ethics Advisory Board, if necessary.

Finally, data produced during the project will be re-usable for as long as the information they contain are relevant for further research purposes.

5. Allocation of resources

5.1. Costs

Costs related to open access to research data in the Horizon Europe programme are eligible costs (article 6.2. C Costs of Purchase) under the conditions defined in the HE Grant Agreement.

5.2. Responsibilities

Data management responsibilities under the project are based on the following figures:

- Joint controllers. In the project there are joint controllers as there are several partners that jointly determine the purposes and means of data processing (art. 26 of the GDPR). Controllers shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with the European GDPR.
- Data processors process personal data only on behalf of the controller.
- DPO provides expert professional knowledge in data protection law and IT security. The duties of the DPO include: to inform and advising the controller or the processor and the employees who carry out processing of their obligations pursuant to the GDPR; to monitor compliance with personal data protection regulation; to provide advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessment and monitor its performance; to cooperate with the supervisory authority; to act as the contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing, and to consult with regard to any other matter (art. 39.1 GDPR).

6. Data security

In the context of the project, where the processing of personal data is not involved, and thus GDPR regulations are not applicable, robust data security measures are nevertheless paramount to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of our research results. We have implemented a comprehensive set of security mechanisms to ensure the protection of the processed data. This includes secure storage protocols, employing encryption techniques to prevent unauthorized access. Access controls will be strictly enforced, limiting data access to authorized personnel with specific roles and responsibilities. Regular audits and monitoring will be conducted to detect and address any potential security vulnerabilities promptly. In addition, a contingency plan for data backup and recovery will be in place to mitigate the risk of data loss. These security measures collectively contribute to the overall resilience of our data management system, assuring the protection of research outcomes without compromising the privacy or confidentiality of individual data subjects.

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Physical security, network security and security of computer systems and files will be considered and encouraged among the consortium to guarantee security of data as well as to prevent unauthorized access, changes to data, disclosure, or destruction of data.

Physical data security:

- Controlling access to buildings, rooms, cabinets where data, computers, media, or hardcopy materials are held.
- Logging the removal of, and access to, media or hardcopy material in storerooms.
- Transporting sensitive data only under exceptional circumstances, even for repair purposes; for example, giving a failed hard drive containing sensitive data to a computer manufacturer may cause a breach of security.

Network security:

- Not storing sensitive data such as those containing personal information on servers or computers connected to an external network, particularly servers that host internet services.
- Firewall protection and security-related upgrades and patches to operating systems to avoid viruses and malicious code.

Security of computer systems and files:

- Locking computer systems with a password.
- Ensuring computer software is up to date.
- Protecting servers by power surge protection systems through line-interactive uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems.
- Implementing password protection and controlled access to data files, for example 'no access', 'read only', 'read and write' or 'administrator-only' permission.
- Controlling access to files, folders, or entire hard drives encryption.
- Not sending personal or confidential data via email or other file transfer means without first encrypting them.
- Destroying data in a consistent manner when needed: deleting files and reformatting a hard drive will not prevent the possible recovery of data; consult our guidance on data disposal.
- Imposing non-disclosure agreements for managers or users of confidential data.

Cloud storage:

The project material is storage is an internal, password-restricted web-based shared working environment, a Google Works Space platform created for CETEC as Project Coordinator for the ViSS communication and information storage.

Only people assigned by ViSS partners and registered by the Project Coordinator can access the ViSS platform. When a partner needs to update (register or unregister) people on the platform, they

must contact the Project Management Team who will guide them until access is complete. For this, you can use the email coordination.

6.1. Compliance with GDPR

This Data Management Plan outlines our commitment to ensuring compliance with applicable international and national regulations, particularly the European Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), throughout the duration of the project. While the processing of personal data is not extensive, it may occur primarily during the implementation of work package 7.2 Public Engagement Strategy. We aim to uphold the principles of data protection and privacy in all project activities.

6.1.1. Purpose

The project underscores the minimization and limitation of personal data processing. Though personal data processing is minimal during the research phase, it may be necessary to process data for disseminating project results, such as events, training, and publicity activities. Any personal data processed will be strictly necessary for the intended purpose and handled in accordance with GDPR principles.

6.1.2. Accuracy

Acknowledging the significance of data accuracy in GDPR compliance, measures will be implemented to ensure that any personal data collected or processed is accurate, relevant, and up to date throughout the project lifecycle. Routine reviews and updates will be conducted to maintain data accuracy.

6.1.3. Integrity and Confidentiality

Upholding the integrity and confidentiality of personal data is paramount. All personal data collected or processed will be treated with the utmost confidentiality, and security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorized access, disclosure, or alteration. Encryption, access controls, and secure storage mechanisms will be employed to safeguard personal data.

6.1.4. Accountability

Maintaining accountability in data processing activities is paramount. Clear roles and responsibilities will be assigned to project team members to ensure compliance with GDPR obligations. Regular audits and assessments will be conducted to monitor compliance and address any issues that may arise.

6.1.5. Personal information

Any personal information collected will be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently in accordance with GDPR requirements. Individuals will be informed of the purpose and legal basis for processing their personal data, and their rights regarding their data will be respected at all times.

6.1.6. Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation

Where feasible, personal data will be anonymized or pseudonymized to minimize risks to data subjects. Anonymization and pseudonymization techniques will be employed to irreversibly dissociate personal data from individual identities, thereby reducing the likelihood of re-identification.

6.1.7. Informed Consent

Where necessary, informed consent will be obtained from data subjects prior to the processing of their personal data. Clear and comprehensible information will be provided to individuals regarding the purposes of data processing, their rights, and how their data will be used. **ViSS involves collecting and processing various personal data, including potentially sensitive information (e.g., ideology, values, health data) during activities like co-creation workshops. Informed consent is required for all personal data processing, as outlined in Article 4(2) of the GDPR, as well as for the use of images, audio/video recordings, and workplace observations. Consent will also cover dissemination activities where such media is used.** The consent form provided to partners includes participants' rights, such as voluntary participation and the possibility to withdraw at any time, with the option to request deletion of any recorded material concerning them (see a template in Annex A of this deliverable).

7. Ethics

All the activities developed along the project will comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example, the Chapter of Fundamental Rights of the EU and the European Convention on Human Rights. In terms of data management, a pivotal role is played by the General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR) as well as the Article 29 Working Party and European Data Protection Supervisor and European Data Protection Board relevant documents.

The tasks for ViSS primarily encompass basic research activities, and the project does not involve humans, animals, or cells. However, it's noteworthy to mention that in the phase of WP 7, which focuses on disseminating and/or conducting surveys about the resulting product of the research carried out during the project, there may be involvement of individuals. This interaction is confined to activities related to product promotion and evaluation and does not entail direct experimentation or manipulation of participants. Regarding any personal data that may be processed during the

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mentioned phase, the rules outlined in the present Data Management Plan will be applied, always safeguarding the rights of the subjects, and respecting European and, if applicable, national data protection regulations. Despite this potential interaction with individuals, any ethical aspects are expected to be addressed, and the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe will be rigorously adhered to. The ViSS Work Package 8.3 Ethics Handbook specifically addresses ethical issues and outlines the 'ethics requirements' that the project must adhere to. Within the framework of deliverable D8.3 Ethics Handbook, all beneficiaries and partner organizations are required to confirm their commitment to upholding the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe, irrespective of the research location.

ViSS partners are not planning to use any harmful material, or process which likely emits harmful materials. They do not use elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants. In any case, all the partners will follow their internal protocols to treat any material according to the national law and EU legislation. In that way, all chemical waste is collected and processed by a central university facility in the Universities involved within the ViSS project. All wastes are recycled or appropriately deposited. Moreover, their respective research does not deal with endangered fauna and/or flora /protected areas.

No experimental tests on humans or animals are planned.

8. References

No state of the art or bibliography has been consulted.

Annex A. Consent form v1

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Participant ID number for this event: _____

Name Activity: XXXXXX

Place and date: XXXXX

Activity Manager: XXXXXX

Project: Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications (ViSS)

1. Responsible for processing personal data:

[Company/Organization Name]

[Address]

[City, State, Zip Code]

[Contact Information]

2. About the ViSS project:

ViSS is a project funded by the European Horizon Fund with Number 101081931.

The European plastics policy promotes bio-based plastics as a solution to the environmental impact of plastics from fossil sources. Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), especially PHBV, are promising biodegradable biopolymers that can replace conventional plastics in applications such as short shelf-life food packaging. The ViSS project will develop a new value chain to produce PHBV from industrial organic waste, creating recyclable and biodegradable packaging. In addition, it will promote collaboration and compliance with EU regulations, disseminating digital tools and resources to increase the acceptance and commercialization of bio-based plastics.

You can find more information about the ViSS project on their website: <https://viss-project.eu>.

3. Purpose of the data processed:

We collect and process your personal data for the control of the activity, such as for legal reasons we will collect your name and surname, your DNI/NIE/Passport and your contact details.

In addition, in the beach cleaning activity in Agua Amarga (Alicante) photographs will be taken in which he could appear if he gives his consent.

4. Type of information collected:

We may collect the following types of personal data:

- Surnames and First Name
- DNI/NIE/Passport
- Photographs of the activity (if expressly consented to)
- Email
- Phone Number

5. Authorization of the use of personal image:

I expressly authorise the University of Alicante to capture and use the image during the activities carried out on the occasion of participation in the activity ____ *Beach clean-up in Agua Amarga in Alicante, on 9 November 2024* ____.

D8.2. Preliminary Data Management. v2.0

Likewise, the University of Alicante, for the purpose described above, is authorised to disseminate, reproduce and distribute these images through any means of communication, for teaching or educational purposes, always respecting the provisions of current regulations, given that the right to one's own image is recognised in Article 18 of the Constitution and regulated by Law 1/1982. of 5 May, on the right to honour, personal and family privacy and one's own image and Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council, of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons.

This authorisation, which is free of charge, is not subject to any time limit or restricted to any specific geographical area, except as provided by law. In compliance with the regulations on the protection of personal data, the University informs that in no case will it transfer the images obtained, and for which this consent is given, to any other public or private entity for a purpose other than that indicated, unless legally established.

6. Data storage and anonymization:

Your personal data will be stored securely and will only be accessible by authorized personnel.

7. Transfer of personal data:

Your personal data will not be shared with third parties other than ViSS partners.

8. Data retention:

We will retain your personal data for as long as necessary to fulfill the purposes outlined in this consent form or as required by law.

9. Your rights:

You have the right to access, rectify, delete and limit the processing of your personal data, as well as to object to it and to the portability of your data, in accordance with the provisions of articles 15 to 22 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Organic Law 3/2018 on the Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights in Spain.

10. Consent:

- I consent to the processing of your personal data for the purposes described in this consent form.
- I expressly authorize the use of my image, for the aforementioned purposes. I understand that this authorization does not grant economic rights of any nature.

Signed (Name and Surname, Place and Date of Signature)

VISS

UK Research
and Innovation

Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, REA or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.
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